

Supplementary Figures for “Inferring the Evolutionary Model of Community-Structuring Traits with Convolutional Kitchen Sinks” by Avery M. Kruger, Vaishaal Shankar, and Jonathan Davies

Supplementary Figure S1. A scatterplot of best R^2 performance for CKS models trained and tested on different numbers of traits. A 128-species phylogeny was evolved with a birth rate of 0.8 and death rate of 0.2. For each number of traits, 4,000 simulations were performed. In each simulation, an early burst (EB) parameter was chosen from a normal distribution (mean = 0, S.D. = 1). The phylogeny was EB-transformed by the parameter, and then the appropriate number of traits were evolved on the transformed tree. A community of 30 species was assembled by probabilistically choosing species based on their exponential distance in trait space from an optimum, set to the mean of each trait across all species. A Convolutional Kitchen Sink model describing the relationship between EB parameter and assembled community was trained on 3,000 simulations. We then predicted the EB parameter of the remaining 1,000 simulations and calculated the R^2 of the fit between prediction and known value of the EB parameter for each number of traits.

Supplementary Figure S2. A scatterplot showing the relationship between matrix dimensions (number of species / data in an observation $n.sp$; window size w ; and feature count f) and compute time of a convolutional kitchen sink process performed with 1 core on a 2021 MacBook Pro using an Apple M1 Pro chip. Axes are log scale. Presented compute time includes calculating the random features of both training and test data, training a ridge regression model on the training data, predicting values on the test data, and calculating the R^2 of the fit between predicted and known values of the test data. Compute time of feature calculation scaled linearly with the product $(n.sp - w + 1) * w * f$ and with the number of rows of data, while compute time of ridge regression scaled approximately with the square of feature count. Predict time and validation time did not scale with dimensions. As overall dimensions increase, the feature calculation quickly dominates total computation time. At some low dimensions, ridge regression takes the most computational time (dimension product $\leq 512,000$ when ridge regression time $> 0.5 * \text{total time}$ in this example).

Supplementary Figure S3. A scatterplot showing the relationship between feature count f and compute time of ridge regression to train a model on data projected by convolutional kitchen sink (CKS). Compute time of ridge regression scales approximately linearly with the square of the number of features.

Supplementary Figure S4. A scatterplot showing the performance of MPD curve models generated on EB transformations (black points) and delta transformations (red points). Models performed similarly (EB, $\text{adj. } R^2 = 0.74$; delta, $R^2 = 0.75$).

Supplementary Figure S5. CKS performance on predicting the mean evolutionary parameter governing assembly of communities assembled on 10 traits with different numbers of unique evolutionary parameters (n_{alphas}). a. 1 parameter. b. 2 parameters. c. 5 parameters. d. 10 parameters. Performance rapidly decreases as the number of independent evolutionary histories of traits increases.

Limiting Similarity

Supplementary Figure S6. A scatterplot of showing the performance of a Convolutional Kitchen Sink model trained and tested on communities assembled by limiting similarity. A 128-species phylogeny was evolved with a birth rate of 0.8 and death rate of 0.2. 2,000 simulations were performed. In each simulation, an early burst (EB) parameter was chosen from a normal distribution (mean = 0, S.D. = 0.5). The phylogeny was EB-transformed by the EB parameter, and then 10 traits were evolved on the transformed tree. A community of 32 species was assembled by sequentially removing the species with the smallest Euclidean distance in trait space from all the other species until 32 species remained. Models describing the relationship between EB parameter and assembled community were trained on 1,350 simulations. We then predicted the EB parameter of the remaining 650 simulations and calculated the R^2 of the fit between prediction and known value of the EB parameter. CKS models with small windows performed best even with few features (window size 5 $R^2 > 0.59$, pictured), but combinations of large window sizes and large feature counts could still perform well (window size 128, feature count 512 $R^2 > 0.48$).

Supplementary Figure S7. A scatterplot of showing the performance of a MPD curve model trained and tested on communities assembled by limiting similarity. A 128-species phylogeny was evolved with a birth rate of 0.8 and death rate of 0.2. 2,000 simulations were performed. In each simulation, an early burst (EB) parameter was chosen from a normal distribution (mean = 0, S.D. = 0.5). The phylogeny was EB-transformed by the EB parameter, and then 10 traits were evolved on the transformed tree. A community of 32 species was assembled by sequentially removing the species with the smallest Euclidean distance in trait space from all the other species until 32 species remained. We calculated standardized MPD for each community across a series of 115 EB transformations, ranging from -3 to 0.1. Models describing the relationship between EB parameter and MPD curve were trained on 1,350 simulations. We then predicted the EB parameter from the MPD curves of the remaining 650 simulations and calculated the R^2 of the fit between prediction and known value of the EB parameter. The model had a slope of 1.05 and $R^2 > 0.51$.